

CATEGORY OF CONCEPT IN LINGUOCULTUROLOGY: HISTORY OF DEVELOPMENT, STRUCTURE, CLASSIFICATION

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ABSTRACT

The article is devoted to a description of the concept of "concept" in cultural linguistics, a comprehensive review and detailed analysis of the history of the study of concepts in linguistic science. Presenting the concept as a basic concept of linguoculturology is the main goal of this article, which is achieved by describing the history of development, analyzing the main directions in the study and research of the structure of the concept.

INTRODUCTION

The system of ideas about the world that a person develops throughout his life is gradually enriched with new knowledge, which is formed into general concepts. This set consists of concepts, since a person, in the process of activity and communication, thinks and acts in the world of concepts that have certain characteristics and properties. The concept is the object of study of a number of sciences, such as cognitive linguistics, cultural studies, linguistic-cultural studies, political science, sociology and ethnopsychology. Linguoculturology considers a set of basic concepts that collectively characterize the manifestations of culture in language and allow one to analyze the relationship between language and culture in development. Currently, the concept is one of the basic concepts of linguoculturology. According to the scientist, a person does not have time or cannot express the meaning fully, sometimes he understands it in his own way depending on social characteristics and conditions [2]. Yu. S. Stepanov characterizes the concept as a cultural-mental-linguistic formation, a clot of culture in the human consciousness. The researcher considers the concept as a "bundle" of ideas, concepts, knowledge and imagination that accompany the word. According to the scientist, in the form of a concept, culture is mentally perceived by a person. On the other hand, according to Yu. S. Stepanov, through a concept, a person himself enters into culture, and sometimes influences it [3]. In linguoculturology, the works of N. D. Arutyunova, Z. Kh. Bizheva, A. Vezhbtskaya, S. G. Vorkachev, V. I. Karasik, V. A. Maslova, G. G. Slyshkin, Yu. S. are devoted to the study of concepts. Stepanova, V.N. Telia, G.V. Tokarev, R.M. Frumkina and others, who consider the concept as a mental unit that is formed in the human mind under the influence of many factors.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Concept is a key concept of linguoculturology, firmly established in linguistics, but it still does not have an unambiguous interpretation, despite the existence of a huge number of definitions and approaches to its study.

The concept in the works of N. D. Arutyunova is interpreted as a concept of everyday philosophy, which is the result of the interaction of folklore, religion, national traditions, feelings and values; the scientist considers the concept as an analogue of ideological terms that are entrenched in the language and contribute to the transmission of the spiritual culture of the people [4]. In this understanding, concepts are culturally significant and value-based concepts of everyday consciousness.

Z. Kh. Bizheva defines a concept as a formulated representation of an ideal concept, reflecting the native speaker's vision of the surrounding reality, which is determined by the traditions of a given culture. She identifies the following linguocultural properties that the concept has: constancy of existence, artistic imagery, preservation of syncretism of root meanings, embeddedness in the system of components of a given culture [5].

V.I. Karasik and G.G. Slyshkin believe that the relationship:

Scientists point out that this scheme is relative, since the relationship between language and culture is a complex phenomenon, and there is also a two-way connection between language and consciousness. In their opinion, the linguocultural concept differs from other concepts used in linguoculturology in its mentality, therefore they understand the concept as a mental formation with a privileged value property [5].

V.I. Karasik and G.G. Slisshkin, analyzing the most important properties of linguocultural concepts, identified their basic characteristics:

- ✓ complexity of existence, based on a comprehensive study of language, consciousness and culture;
- ✓ mentality that distinguishes a concept from other units in linguoculturology;
- ✓ axiological, since the linguocultural concept differs from other mental units in its value element;
- ✓ conventionality (the division of consciousness is carried out for the purpose of research) and vagueness (the concept has no specific boundaries);
- ✓ variability, since over time the perception of the content of the concept may change;
- ✓ limitation by the consciousness of the carrier, due to the existence of the concept in the individual or collective consciousness;
- ✓ three-component - the concept includes value, image and conceptual components;
- ✓ polyappealability (the existence of multiple ways of appealing to any linguocultural concept);
- ✓ multidimensionality - traditional units of linguoculturology are used to model the concept;
- ✓ methodological openness and polyclassification (within the framework of linguoculturology, the use of both linguistic and non-linguistic methods is acceptable;
- ✓ concepts can be classified based on various characteristics) [3].

By concepts, V. A. Maslova means the culturally determined basic elements of the picture of the world, which are significant both for the linguistic individual and for the linguistic and cultural community. The researcher considers such abstract names as will, sin, homeland, conscience, fate, etc. to be key cultural concepts. She also notes that the study of these words is very relevant, since key concepts of culture occupy an important place in the linguistic consciousness of the people.

G.V. Tokarev describes the concept as a historically developing element of the conceptual sphere. From the point of view of the cultural-semiotic approach, the concept is considered as a global, multilateral mental unit, which is characterized by the following features:

- ✓ conditioned by cultural and historical events;
- ✓ the presence of an internal structure consisting of simpler meanings;
- ✓ heterogeneity of content;
- ✓ wide volume;
- ✓ expression by various symbolic representations.

A concept is a multidimensional formation, a necessary condition for the existence of which and its inclusion in the conceptual sphere of a particular people is the presence of a certain structure. Scientists express different points of view regarding the structure of the linguocultural concept. For example, S. Kh. Lyapin notes that the concept is a multidimensional culturally significant socio-psychic formation in the collective consciousness, which is objectified in linguistic form [3]. S. V. Ivanova identifies linguistic, cognitive, cultural and psychological components in the structure of the concept and

emphasizes that value assessment is considered the main condition for the formation of the concept.

V.I. Karasik considers the concept as a multidimensional linguistic formation that contains a conceptual basis, internal form, distributional properties, valence connections and cultural properties. He also identifies three sides in the structure of the concept:

- ✓ conceptual - designation of the concept in language;
- ✓ figurative - perception of the features of objects and events existing in memory or representations through vision, hearing, taste and smell;
- ✓ the value side is determined by the relevance of the concept for man and society.

Yu. S. Stepanov's reasoning about the structure of a concept deserves special attention, according to whom, the structure of a concept includes everything that turns it into a fact of culture: etymology, history in the form of the main features of content, presentation, evaluation, etc. [4]. The scientist notes that the concept has a "layered" structure, each of the "layers" is the result of the cultural life of different times, that is, the concept consists of historically different layers, different in etymology, time of formation, and meaning. The concept, according to the researcher, includes the following components:

- ✓ the main, relevant feature - significant for all speakers of a language and culture, which, verbally speaking, is a means of communication between representatives of a certain people;
- ✓ additional, passive sign - available to a certain social group;
- ✓ etymological sign or internal form - the origin of the word is not realized in its external form, and therefore is the least important for culture bearers, however, as the scientist notes, other meanings arise and exist on this sign.

G.V. Tokarev in the structural model of the concept identifies two main types of content:

- ✓ the first type includes elements of knowledge that have value and importance for everyone - the layer of the concept that contains knowledge of this type, according to the scientist, is called universal;
- ✓ the second type includes nationally specific knowledge that is characteristic of a certain group united by a common language, history and culture - this heterogeneous layer of the concept containing such knowledge is called cultural [2].

V. A. Maslova describes the concept as a complex that, in addition to the content, assessment and attitude of a person to the described object, includes the following components: universal (universal); national-cultural, conditioned by life in certain cultural conditions; social - this component determines belonging to any social stratum; group, determined by belonging to a certain age or gender group; individual-personal, the formation of which is influenced by personal characteristics (education, upbringing, individual experience, psychophysiological characteristics) [5]. In modern linguistics, the structure of a concept is also represented in the form of a circle, consisting of a core, a subnuclear zone and a periphery. Belonging to a particular zone is determined by the perception of a sign by a native speaker. The concept is described as a list of features as the brightness decreases from the core to the periphery. This point of view is shared by many scientists. For example, as V.I. Karasik and G.G. Slyshkin argue, the concept appears around a value-emphasized point of consciousness, around which there are imaginary vectors. The most significant of these vectors determine the core of the concept, the less important - the periphery. As the distance

from the nucleus increases, the associations become less bright. The name of the concept is determined by a unit of language or speech that actualizes the central point [4].

Various criteria can serve as the basis for classifying concepts. For example, T.V. Gonnova proposes a division of concepts according to internal or external assessment: regulatory concepts ("work", "feat", "happiness") express internal assessment; parametric - connected with cultural concepts using an intermediary link ("age", "status", "time", "space"). From a pragmatic point of view, A. Ya. Gurevich divides linguocultural concepts into universal (time, space, cause, change, movement) and social (cultural) (freedom, law, justice, labor, wealth, property). The authors of the discourse classification proceed from the principle of ways of mastering the world - scientific, artistic and everyday [1], therefore, scientific, artistic and everyday concepts are distinguished. D. S. Likhachev proposes a classification based on sociological criteria. The scientist divides concepts into universal ("death", "life"), ethnic ("fatherland", "intelligentsia"), group ("stage" for the actor and spectator), individual (determining the level of culture and value system of a particular person). Belonging to the service sphere of consciousness is also a criterion for the classification of linguocultural concepts. According to Yu. S. Stepanov, language units that participate in the formation of the content of cultural values can be noted not only within one language, but also within the framework of an interlingual style of thinking [3].

The most common classification, in our opinion, is the division of concepts into universal and national. Universal concepts are presented in the form of universal human knowledge and do not have cultural specificity (good - evil, joy - grief, love - hate). In addition to universal ones, there are concepts focused on a specific ethnic group. According to A. Wierzbicka, just as thoughts can be thought out in one language, so feelings can be experienced within one linguistic consciousness and not another. The scientist distinguishes autochthonous concepts (containing general and national components in their meaning) and protoconcepts (universal concepts). V. P. Neroznak believes that the concepts of national culture are reflected in non-equivalent vocabulary, which serves as material for compiling a list of basic national concepts. V. A. Maslova gives examples of categories of Russian culture: "Will", "Share", "Intelligence", "Collectiveness", etc.

The system of concepts in which the linguistic picture of the world and the collective linguistic consciousness of an ethnos are manifested represents the conceptual sphere of a particular culture. The conceptsphere (D. S. Likhachev's term), representing a structure that changes in time and space of a separate ethnic group, consists of universal concepts that ensure mutual understanding between peoples, and national ones, inherent in a particular culture and enshrined in language, traditions and beliefs. National culture has its own worldviews and values, on the basis of which stereotypes associated with a given people are formed. In the concept sphere of each ethnic group, concepts are distinguished that are more stable and significant for the national culture - key concepts (constants). These basic units of the picture of the world are important both for the linguistic personality and for the linguistic and cultural community [2].

Despite the confident formation and rapid development of linguocultural studies as a science, at present there is no common understanding of the term linguocultural analysis. As noted by E.I. Zinovieva and E.E. Yurkov, this term refers to different methods: conceptual

analysis, discourse analysis, methods of applying dictionary entries, etc. The concept of conceptual analysis in modern linguistics is ambiguous. This phrase, as S. E. Nikitina points out, can be considered both as an analysis of concepts and as a certain type of research, for example, analysis using concepts or analysis in which concepts are the ultimate units [2]. E. I. Zinovieva and E. E. Yurkov, meaning the analysis of concepts by conceptual analysis, consider it advisable to use in the analysis a methodology that is a set of proposed research methods: determining the connections of a concept with other concepts of the same culture, at the level of paradigm and syntagma, which is proposed by S.E. Nikitina, and the study of the compatibility of abstract names and imaginary fields.

CONCLUSIONS

Based on the above methods, scientists propose several stages of researching the concept:

- ✓ studying the origin of a concept word to determine its deep meaning;
- ✓ dictionary data analysis;
- ✓ identification of additional conceptual features using distributional analysis of the compatibility of a given word;
- ✓ analysis of applications in metaphorical meaning; study of derivational derivatives of the main word;
- ✓ determination of concept connections in the conceptual sphere of language at the paradigm level;
- ✓ using associative dictionaries or conducting an associative experiment to determine the imaginary field of the word-concept being studied.

M. V. Pimenova writes that the study of concepts is carried out in several stages:

- ✓ study of the lexical meaning and internal form of a word; definition of synonyms for a given word;
- ✓ analysis of ways to implement the concept in the linguistic picture of the world;
- ✓ identifying ways of conceptualization, studying metaphors and metonymy;
- ✓ studies of events that occurred in time and/or space, in which the presence of a subject, object, purpose, conditions, time and place is assumed and determined by certain causes of occurrence.

Thus, in linguoculturology, language is considered one of the main ways of forming basic concepts - concepts in the human mind. Through the concept, the word penetrates into the linguistic picture of the world and is located in it, interacting with other lexical units. The concept is the central category in the scientific and linguistic description of the linguistic reflection of the world. Developed on the basis of personal and cultural experience, concepts are a spiritual heritage in the minds of the people, the result of knowledge of the surrounding world, reflecting the linguistic picture and national mentality.

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